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INDICATORS OF THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF OBESITY AND ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

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ANNOTATION

According to statistics, the number of obese children is steadily increasing every year. In this regard, attention to the problem of the metabolic syndrome should be paid already at the initial stages of its formation, from early childhood, in order to prevent the development of cardiovascular diseases in the future. In childhood, the syndromes that are components of the metabolic syndrome form gradually and are often asymptomatic. Obesity is one of the first to develop, arterial hypertension joins at the age of 10 years, and impaired glucose tolerance in the puberty period. Dyslipidemia can occur at any age, including only in adults. In children with metabolic syndrome, anesthetic management also has a number of features, both in organizational terms and in terms of management tactics in conditions of an increased risk of complications.

Key words: obesity; abdominal obesity; arterial hypertension; risk factors; children and teenagers

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SEMIZLIK VA ARTERIAL GIPERTENZIYA FONIDA BOLALAR VA O'SGIRLARDA YURAK-QON TOMIR TIZIMINING KO'RSATGICHLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Statistik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, semiz bolalar soni har yili barqaror o'sib bormoqda. Shu munosabat bilan, kelajakda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari rivojlanishining oldini olish uchun metabolik sindrom muammosiga uning shakllanishining dastlabki bosqichlarida, erta bolalikdan boshlab e'tibor qaratish lozim. Bolalikda metabolik sindromning tarkibiy qismlari bo'lgan sindromlar asta-sekin shakllanadi va ko'pincha asemptomatikdir. Semirib ketish birinchilardan bo'lib rivojlanadi, arterial gipertenziya 10 yoshda qo'shiladi va balog'at yoshida glyukoza bardoshliliksi buziladi. Dislipidemiya har qanday yoshda, shu jumladan faqat kattalarda paydo bo'lishi mumkin. Metabolik sindromi bo'lgan bolalarda anesteziyani boshqarish ham tashkiliy jihatdan, ham asoratlar xavfi yuqori bo'lgan sharoitlarda boshqaruv taktikasi nuqtai nazaridan bir qator xususiyatlarga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: semizlik; qorin bo'shlig'idagi semirish; arterial gipertenziya; xavf omillari; bolalar va o'smirlar.

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ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ СЕРДЕЧНО-СОСУДИСТОЙ СИСТЕМЫ У ДЕТЕЙ И ПОДРОСТКОВ НА ФОНЕ ОЖИРЕНИЯ И АРТЕРИАЛЬНОЙ ГИПЕРТОНИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

По данным статистики, количество детей, страдающих ожирением, с каждым годом неуклонно растет. В связи с этим внимание к проблеме метаболического синдрома должно быть обращено уже на начальных этапах его формирования, с раннего детского возраста, для осуществления профилактики развития сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний в дальнейшем. В детском возрасте синдромы, являющиеся составными частями метаболического синдрома, формируются постепенно и зачастую бессимптомно. Одним из первых развивается ожирение, в возрасте 10 лет присоединяется артериальная гипертензия, в пубертатном периоде — нарушение толерантности к глюкозе. Дислипидемия может возникнуть в любом возрастном периоде, в том числе только во взрослом. У детей с метаболическим синдромом ряд особенностей имеет и анестезиологическое обеспечение — как в организационном плане, так и в отношении тактики ведения в условиях повышенного риска осложнений.

Ключевые слова: ожирение; абдоминальное ожирение; артериальная гипертензия; факторы риска; дети и подростки.

The urgency of the problem. The data of recent years prove that left ventricular hypertrophy is an independent risk factor for the development of cardiovascular diseases and mortality in adults [2,6]. According to the authors, the formation of eccentric LVH occurs earlier in children with borderline arterial hypertension on the background of obesity [1,2], and there are also studies confirming the earliest development of signs of left ventricular remodeling in patients with obesity and insulin resistance [3,5].

Materials and methods: 61 adolescents aged 15 to 18 years with exogenous constitutional obesity were examined. The selection criterion for patients was the determination of BMI and waist size in children and adolescents with identified overweight and/or obesity, which was above the 97th percentile for a certain age and sex (WHO 2006). The study included 28 girls (46%) and 33 (54%) boys, whose mean age was 17.01 ± 0.21 years. Groups were divided based on BMI. Group 1 consisted of 23 adolescents with overweight and obesity of the 1st degree (30.2±1.3 kg/m²), group 2 consisted of 20 adolescents with a BMI of 33.4±1.1 kg/m². Group 3 included 18 teenagers with BMI - 36.1±1.4 kg/m². The control group consisted of 20 healthy adolescents of the same age with a BMI of 22.5±0.9 kg/m². The study was carried out by general clinical standard examination. Body weight was assessed using percentile tables of the ratio of linear height to body weight or body mass index (Quetelet index) for a certain age and sex (WHO, 1998). The volume of the waist (WT) and hips (OB) was determined, the ratio of which is an indicator of abdominal obesity. With WC/VR values >0.85 in girls and >0.9 in boys, their condition was regarded as abdominal obesity (IDF, 1997). Arterial hypertension was diagnosed in accordance with the criteria developed by the Committee of Experts of the All-Russian Scientific Society of Cardiology and the Association of Pediatric Cardiologists of Russia (Moscow, 2009) [4].

Morphometric parameters of the myocardium (myocardial mass - LVML, myocardial mass index - LVMI, thickness of the interventricular septum - VTVS, thickness of the posterior wall of the left ventricle - PVSLV) were assessed by ultrasound echocardiography using an Aloka Alpha-7 ultrasound scanner with a cardiological package. The laboratory study included the determination of the level of cholesterol, high density lipoproteins and triglycerides in the blood serum using a biochemical analyzer. Serum insulin levels were determined by enzyme immunoassay.

Insulin resistance was assessed using the HOMAR index, which reflects the ratio of glucose (in mg/dL) and insulin (in μIU/mL). The

criterion for the presence of IR was considered to be an index value above 2.7 conventional units.

Results of the study: in accordance with the set goal, we determined the relationship between the degree of BMI and the level of systolic and diastolic pressure in adolescents.

The results of the study showed that the level of systolic and diastolic blood pressure for all time intervals was significantly higher in adolescents of the 3rd group (135.2 ± 9.1 mm Hg, p<0.05) and p<0.05) compared with the values of adolescents with obesity of 1 and 2 degrees (118.3 ± 7.5 and 123.2 ± 6.7 mm Hg) At the same time, a direct correlation was found between BMI and systolic pressure, diastolic pressure and average pressure per day (r=0.602, r=0.589 and r=0.603, respectively, p<0.01 for all parameters). It should be noted that according to the results of the study of blood pressure among overweight and obese adolescents, “white coat hypertension” was detected in 22.9% of cases, labile AH in 16.3%, and stable AH in 13.1%. At the same time, a stable form was significantly more often detected in obesity of the 3rd degree (6.5%) compared with obesity of the 1st degree and obesity of the 2nd degree (3.2% and 3.2%, respectively). An echocardiographic study showed that in obesity in combination with arterial hypertension, a structural-geometric reorganization of the left ventricular myocardium occurs. In this case, first of all, the wall thickness increases. We found a statistically significant relationship between BMI and the thickness of the posterior wall of the left ventricle (r=0.588; p<0.01) as well as the thickness of the interventricular septum (r=0.501; p<0.05). It should be noted that hypertrophy of the left ventricular walls is initially formed as an adaptive reaction of the myocardium to the pressure load and ensures that the contractile function of the left ventricle corresponds to the increased load. The main indicators characterizing left ventricular myocardial hypertrophy are myocardial mass and left ventricular myocardial mass index. Our data showed that the incidence of left ventricular hypertrophy was 43.4% in group 1, 50% in group 2, and 61.1% in group 3. At the same time, when analyzing the mass index of the left ventricular myocardium, depending on the variant of arterial hypertension, no significant differences were found. With white coat hypertension - 35.7±3.4 g/m².7, with labile hypertension - 35.9±4.7 g/m².7, and with stable hypertension - 36.4±4.6 g/m². 7. This fact suggests that it is obesity that makes a significant contribution to the degree of increase in the mass of the left ventricle. Restructuring of the geometry of the left ventricle was detected in almost 1/3 of adolescents with obesity, while in group 1 - 30.4%, in group 2 - 35.0% and in group

3 - 33.3%. Eccentric hypertrophy of the left ventricle was diagnosed in 16.3% of patients, concentric remodeling in 11.4%. It should be noted that concentric left ventricular hypertrophy is associated with the maximum risk of cardiovascular complications; in our study, it occurred in 4.9% of cases and only in the group of adolescents with grade 3 obesity. Structural geometric restructuring included a change in the geometry of not only the left ventricle, but also the left atrium. Thus, the difference in the average values of the dimensions of the left atrium was revealed between all observation groups (31.4±1.2 mm; 31.8±0.8 mm and 34.5±1.4 mm in groups 1, 2 and 3, respectively). The correlation between the size of the left atrium and BMI was also statistically significant ($r=0.608$; $p<0.01$). Most likely, changes in the structure of the left atrium are the earliest stage of myocardial remodeling. The compensatory response of the cardiovascular system in response to obesity also affected central hemodynamics. Thus, the volume of circulating blood and the total peripheral vascular resistance changed. The minute volume of blood circulation gradually increased with the progression of obesity (5.5±1.1 l/min, 5.8±0.9 l/min and 6.2±1.1 l/min, respectively, in groups 1, 2 and 3), which indirectly indicates an increase in the volume of circulating blood. The increase in minute volume was accompanied by a decrease in total peripheral vascular resistance with an increase in body weight (1318.8±289.1 dyn/cm/s-5; 1299.9±274.3 dyn/cm/s-5 and 1287.4±284.1 dyn/cm/s-5 respectively in groups 1, 2 and 3) Also, the total peripheral resistance depended on the type of arterial hypertension, so in labile arterial hypertension this indicator was 1287.8±250.7 dyn/cm/s-5, and at stable 1325.6±301.5 dyn/cm/s-5, which characterized the depletion of the body's adaptive capabilities and an increase in the total peripheral vascular resistance. It was also of interest to us to study the state of lipid and carbohydrate metabolism, in violation of which the risk of atherogenic changes in the vascular wall increases sharply. To determine the type of carbohydrate metabolism disorder, a glucose tolerance test was conducted, which revealed disorders in 22.9% of adolescents, mainly in groups 2 and 3 (30% and 44.4%). But even a glucose tolerance test does not always reflect the degree of carbohydrate metabolism disorder, in connection with which we studied the level of immunoreactive insulin in the blood, followed by the determination of the HOMA R index. The results of the study showed that the level of immunoreactive insulin was statistically

significantly higher in obese children (14.2±1.2 μ IU/ml; 16.7±1.5 μ IU/ml; 19.3±2.1 μ IU/ml; in 1, 2 and 3 groups, respectively) compared with the control group (9.3 ± 0.8 μ IU/ml), at a normal level of fasting glucose. The incidence of insulin resistance in obese patients was 24.5%. As obesity progressed, the incidence of insulin resistance increased. Thus, in group 1 insulin resistance was detected in 13.0%, in group 2 in 25% and in group 3 in 38.8% of cases. Correlation analysis revealed direct relationships between the level of immunoreactive insulin and BMI ($r=0.545$; $p<0.01$), as well as the relationship between BMI and the HOMA index ($r=0.704$; $p<0.01$). The data obtained allow us to conclude that the level of insulin directly and significantly depends on the excess accumulation of fat. When comparing insulin resistance and the form of arterial hypertension, it was found that in adolescents with white coat hypertension, insulin resistance was diagnosed in 3.2%, in adolescents with labile AH in 8.1% and in children with stable AH in 11.4% of cases. This proves that insulin resistance is a key mechanism around which a chain of hemodynamic and metabolic pathologies is formed. When analyzing the results of the lipid composition of the serum of the studied contingent of adolescents, it was found that as obesity progressed, both the level of triglycerides ($r=0.621$; $p<0.01$) and the level of low-density lipoproteins ($r=0.501$; $p<0.05$) increased, and the level of high-density lipoproteins decreased ($r=0.703$; $p<0.001$). Thus, the data obtained show that the presence of dyslipidemia against the background of insulin resistance, accompanied by hypertension and obesity, indicates the formation of a complete metabolic syndrome in this contingent of adolescents, which in our studies was detected in 19.6% of cases, incomplete metabolic syndrome was diagnosed. 36.0% of cases.

Conclusions: the development of myocardial hypertrophy is affected by body weight, blood pressure, vasoconstriction processes, as well as insulin resistance and atherogenic dyslipidemia. These parameters can serve as early markers of myocardial hypertrophy. Also, in children with obesity and hypertension, in 1/5 of cases, a complete metabolic syndrome was detected and in 1/3 of cases, an incomplete metabolic syndrome, which requires immediate treatment of this condition in order to prevent early complications and disability in adolescents in the adult period.

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